

Reliable in-Vehicle perception and decision-making in complex environmental conditions

Grant Agreement Number: 101069614

D.7.1: EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness

Document Identification			
Status	Final	Due Date	Tuesday 28 February 2023
Version	1.0	Submission Date	Friday 24 February 2023
Related WP	WP7	Document Reference	D.7.1
Related Deliverable(s)		Dissemination Level	PU
Lead Participant	SEAB	Document Type:	R
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This project has received funding under grant agreement No 101069614. It is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Document History			
Version	Date	Modified by	Modification reason
0.1	24/10/2022	Elena Krikigianni, Evangelia Latsa	Creation of the ToC
0.2	02/11/2022	Panagiotis, Lytrivis, Irini Krimpa	Comments and improvement of the ToC
0.3	12/12/2022	Elena Krikigianni, Evangelia Latsa	Input in all chapters
0.4	27/01/2023	Panagiotis, Lytrivis, Irini Krimpa, Vasilis Roungas	Comments and refinements
0.5	10/02/2023	Elena Krikigianni, Evangelia Latsa	Additional input throughout the document and refinements
0.6	16/02/2023	Michael Buchholz	Comments throughout the document
0.7	20/02/2023	Elena Krikigianni	Release of deliverable for peer review
0.8	23/02/2023	Ahrabian Alireza, Nikoletta Karitsioti	Addressing peer review comments
0.9	23/02/2023	Panagiotis Lytrivis	Final quality check
1.0	24/02/2023	Elena Krikigianni	Final version to be submitted

Quality Control		
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Executive Summary

Communication, dissemination, and social awareness processes are essential to assure the success of a project as ambitious and visionary as EVENTS. Funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme, the aim of EVENTS is to create a robust and resilient perception and decision-making system for Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) to manage various types of "events" on the horizon. These situations are creating challenges for CAVs that should be overcome, in order to enable safe and reliable automated driving in such cases.

The present document is considered as a living document and is connected to Task 7.1: EVENTS Communication & dissemination and Task 7.4: Social innovation & gender equality, within Work Package WP7: Outreach.

The current document provides the communication and dissemination strategy and plan, focused also on the EVENTS social awareness. The strategic plan for EVENTS Communication and Dissemination is crafted by introducing a 5-step approach, which includes the identification of relevant objectives and relevant target audiences, in order to efficiently anchor the project's vision, ideas, results and outcomes to targeted audiences towards the definition of key messages and the identification of appropriate channels and tools.

It also summarizes all the communication activities performed by EVENTS' partners until M06 and those still planned and provides a status monitoring of both dissemination and communication activities through the measurement of a set of identified KPIs. In communication, dissemination and social awareness, activities are inter-linked in EVENTS, and constitute a substantial part of the communication strategy, ensuring a strong future exploitation. Related communication actions and dissemination activities have been assigned from the early beginning of the project to each of the consortium partners. Reference is also given to the scientific approach of EVENTS project, as well as to the clustering activities and how cross fertilization can be achieved by creating common synergies.

EVENTS communication, dissemination and social awareness plan, is considered as a strategically planned process, which commenced at the outset of the project and which will remain active throughout its entire lifetime. Its ultimate aim is to achieve the promotion of the project and its results, towards using strategic and targeted measures for communicating the outcomes to a multitude of audiences and engaging them in a two-way exchange.

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Abbreviations & Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
ASAM	Association for Standardization of Automation and Measuring Systems
CA	Consortium Agreement
California PATH	California Partners for Advanced Transportation Technology (PATH)
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message according to EN 302 637-2
CAVs	Connected and Automated Vehicles
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CPM	Collective Perception Messages
DoA	Decision of Actions
DSP applications	Digital Signal Processing applications
ECTA	European Competitive Telecommunications Association
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERTRAC WG	European Road Transport Research Advisory Council Working Group
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EUCAD2023	European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving 2023
EUCAR	European Council for Automotive Research & Development
FRAV	Working Group on Functional Requirements for Automated and Autonomous
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
HE	Horizon Europe
ICT	Information & Communication Technologies
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITS	Intelligent transportation Systems

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
JARI	Japan Automobile Research Institute
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LANs	Local Area Networks
LoI	Letter Of Intent
M01, M02 etc.	Month 1, Month 2, etc
ML-based scene	Machine Learning based scene
MRM	Minimum Risk Manoeuvre
MS	Microsoft
MS	Milestone
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OEMs	Original Equipment Manufacturer
ORE	Open Research Europe
PDI	Physical and digital infrastructure
PMs	Person Months
PO	Project Officer
PU	Public Use
R&D	Research & Development
SAE	Society of Automobile Engineers
SMEs	Small – Medium Enterprises
SOTIF	Safety Of The Intended Functionality
SW	Software
T-IV	Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles
TRB	Transport Research Board
V2X	Vehicle to everything
VAM	VRU awareness message
VMAD	Validation Methods for Automated Driving
VRU	Vulnerable Road Users
VU	Vulnerable Users

1. Introduction

The current deliverable, D7.1: EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness, constitutes a key reference document for all the communication, dissemination, and social awareness activities to be implemented within WP7 of EVENTS project and it is intended as a living document through the project's lifetime.

This document contains all the important information needed to facilitate the communication, dissemination, and social awareness efforts of the EVENTS consortium. It presents the EVENTS project's dissemination, communication, and social awareness strategy to be followed by the consortium to guarantee high visibility, accessibility and promotion of the project's vision, key findings and research results towards ensuring a successful future exploitation. Furthermore, it will ensure that impactful activities have been planned to engage stakeholders, create awareness, and promote EVENTS. The ultimate goal of this document is the effective communication and dissemination of project's assets, course and key outcomes to the identified related target audiences.

As a matter of fact, this document aims to ensure that clear communication, dissemination and social awareness objectives have been set, key target audiences have been identified and well defined, tailored messages have been crafted per each target audience, the appropriate channels will be used, sufficient communication materials and resources will be produced, and the right evaluation methods will be implemented.

1.1 Purpose of the document

EVENTS's Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness strategy and plan are designed to provide an initial, detailed, and comprehensive framework for the communication, dissemination and social awareness activities to be performed within EVENTS project. It constitutes an effective tool to amplify the impact of the project results and outcomes, to optimize their value and foster their active and concrete use in systems and practices at local, regional, national, European and international level. The set of processes presented below will remain active throughout the project lifetime (in line with Grant Agreement (GA), Articles 16.3 & 17) to facilitate the project's consortium to reach a wide range of relevant audiences while at the same time to disseminate and communicate EVENTS's results to the industrial, academic and Small to Medium Enterprises (SMEs) domain.

1.2 Intended readership

D7.1: EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness is a public deliverable and constitutes a very useful guidance, addressed not only to the consortium members, but also to any interested reader (i.e., Public (PU) dissemination level).

It is primarily written for the European Commission (EC), Project Officer (PO) and the consortium members of the EVENTS project as a useful guidance for the planning and contribution to EVENTS communication, dissemination and social awareness activities. More specifically, it serves as a tool that helps them understand the project's outreach objectives and how these could contribute to raise awareness in an efficient and effective way.

Nevertheless, special effort and focus have been, also, given on making this report a stand-alone comprehensible document for the general public.

1.3 Document Structure

Section 1 introduces the purpose of the document, the intended readership, the document structure and the provision of key definitions.

Section 2 provides all the necessary information regarding the EVENTS communication and dissemination strategy and plan.

Section 3 presents the scientific approach of the EVENTS project.

Section 4 describes the EVENTS clustering and networking activities.

Section 5 outlines the EVENTS social awareness strategy and plan.

Section 6 highlights both the performed and planned communication and dissemination activities of EVENTS project.

Section 7 underlines the evaluation and monitoring processes of the EVENTS communication and dissemination activities.

Section 8 analyses the partners' roles and efforts.

Finally, section 9 summarizes the concluding remarks of *D7.1: EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness*.

1.4 Definitions

Communication and dissemination can be considered as the different sides of the same coin. The boundaries between some of their activities are often blurry and sometimes can create confusion. More specifically, certain tools and activities (e.g., a magazine article that is published for communication purposes can trigger the interest of potential stakeholders in using the presented project outcomes and thus it has automatically become a dissemination tool) can oscillate between communication and dissemination, depending on the target audience and content [1]. Thus, what differentiates them are the objectives they have, their main point of focus, and the target audiences they address. In this sub-chapter, a clarification on the terminology

as well as a clear distinction of their corresponding activities is given, by shedding light on their differences.

Communication refers to the project promotion, and its themes and the challenges which will be encountered. Consortium partners must undertake all means they have at their disposal to efficiently promote the action and its results, by spreading targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in a strategic and effective way to achieve a two-way exchange. A comprehensive communication plan should include a clear definition of its objectives, define key messages tailored to each target audience and set out an accurate roadmap of activities [2]. This standardisation will more effectively promote the creation of communication strategies that can be adopted easier for any situation.

Dissemination is a process used to enhance the impact, visibility, and credibility of a project. It refers to the public disclosure of the results of the project by appropriate means. Dissemination may be achieved by sharing information concerning the project and the publication of the project's findings using traditional media channels (newsletters, publications, news media coverage), and digital media (social media). Dissemination may also be achieved through the publication of project results and outputs in peer reviewed scientific journals, presentations in scientific conferences, and industry related events [3].

According to the recent (2022) Horizon Europe Programme Guide [4], both communication and dissemination processes are mandatory and vital for Horizon Europe projects. It is also important that results remain protected at all times. Their differences are presented in the following table 1:

Table 1 Difference between Dissemination & Communication in Horizon Europe projects

Communication	Dissemination
<i>Covers the whole project (including results)</i>	<i>Covers project results only</i>
<i>Starts at the outset of the project</i>	<i>Happens only once results are available</i>
<i>Multiple audiences Beyond the project's own community, including the media and general public Multiplier effect.</i>	<i>Specialist audiences Groups that may use the results in their own work, including peer groups, industry, professional organisations, policymakers</i>
<i>Informing and engaging with society, to show how it can benefit from research</i>	<i>Enabling the take-up and use of results</i>
<i>Legal reference: Grant Agreement Articles 16.3, 17, Annex 5.</i>	

2. EVENTS Communication & Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Overview of the plan

2.1.1 EVENTS approach to dissemination & communication

The dissemination and communication approach which will be followed by EVENTS project is analysed in the following five-step procedure as depicted in the figure 1 below:

Figure 1 EVENTS Communication & Dissemination approach

The afore-mentioned approach aims to address most of the basic elements of EVENTS communication and dissemination, namely the target audiences, the key messages for each target audience, the communication means and channels to be used, as well as the time frame for delivering the messages. It, also, includes a monitoring and evaluation process, as a mean to ensure the efficiency of the communication and dissemination strategy and allow for the smooth coordination of individual communications and dissemination activities throughout the project lifetime.

The effectiveness of EVENTS communication and dissemination strategy will be achieved by addressing a set of simple questions, according to a combination of Lasswell model of five levels of communication [5] and Berlo's S-M-C-R Model [6], such

as “Who are the key audiences?”, “What do these audiences know now?”, “What do we need them to know?”, “What message or messages do they need to receive?” and “What is the most effective mode/media to deliver these messages?”. The successful implementation of this approach will maximise the communication’s impact and it will ensure the project’s higher visibility to targeted audiences.

2.1.2 Key concepts and objectives

As set out in the project grant agreement, the main objectives of WP7: *Outreach*, shaping the targets of the EVENTS communication and dissemination strategy, are summarised as follows:

- To **develop** a comprehensive Communication and Dissemination strategy and plan for soundly promoting the progress, technical & scientific results of EVENTS, maximizing its outreach and streamlining wide awareness to a wide range of stakeholders at all geographical levels and relevant sectors via the establishment of high quality impactful systematic tools, channels and means for communicating the project objectives, activity, progress, impact and outcomes.
- To **make sure** that Communication and Dissemination strategy and plan is up-to-date.
- To **coordinate** the scientific outreach through the development of Open Access scientific material and participation in scientific and industrial events, conferences, seminars, fora, working groups, etc.
- To **ensure** successful implementation and viability of the project’s innovative ideas.
- To **liaise** with relevant Research & Development (R&D) projects and partners in European Union (EU) and beyond, fostering international cooperation, ensuring knowledge exchange, interoperability as well as wide market penetration.
- To **contribute**, upon invitation by the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA), to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between Horizon Europe (HE) /Horizon 2020 (H2020) supported actions.
- To **investigate** social innovation pathways at different levels and sectors.
- To **promote** gender equality and ensure women’s equal access and opportunities for participation in the technical/ scientific fields covered by EVENTS.

More specifically, as defined in the Description of Action (DoA) (section 2.2), within EVENTS WP7 particular focus will be given on the overall measures and steps to maximise EVENTS’s impact, which are summarised as follow:

- **Motivate** EVENTS partners into engaging their networks of actors and build relationships, through intensive networking, with related R&D initiatives, organisations, networks and fora to discuss the EVENTS results, share resource/data, examine interoperability issues and spread good practices through clustering activities.
- **Engage** scientific, technical, business, institutional and governmental audiences from the EU and globally to efficiently disseminate the EVENTS results to the widest audience possible and encourage feedback.
- **Demonstrate** Cooperative Connected Autonomous Mobility (CCAM) experts the capabilities of the EVENTS perception and decision-making algorithms and the Operational Design Domain (ODD) extension.
- **Demonstrate** to various stakeholders the business value of the proposed EVENTS developments.
- **Promote** the multi-disciplinary character of the project to attract wide range of audiences and to showcase how EVENTS will make CAVs more robust, safer, affordable and effective.
- **Demonstrate** to the citizens the added value of a robust, transparent and accurate perception and decision-making system for future CAVs and, thus, for the quality of their everyday life and the societal and environmental benefits from the use of it, enhancing overall user acceptance of CCAM.

2.1.3 Identification of target audiences (to whom)

A vital key to the successful implementation of EVENTS's communication and dissemination intentions is a thorough understanding of the key target audiences that the project needs to reach out and engage with, as well as their special characteristics, behaviours, needs, motivations, and frustrations.

EVENTS plan sets out specific target stakeholders and groups covering the full range of potential users in the connected and automated vehicles industry.

An initial mapping of EVENTS stakeholders' community has been developed early in advance (since the proposal phase), including the following stakeholders (Table 2):

Table 2 EVENTS stakeholders' community

EVENTS stakeholders' community
Automotive Industry Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), Tier 1
Institutions & Committees (Policy & decision makers, Authorities in international, European and local level, Standardisation bodies)
Associations (CCAM, End-user associations)
Platforms and fora

Information & Communication Technologies (ICT) players (ICT SMEs, Service and Technology Providers, Software Suppliers, Infrastructure Suppliers)
Research Community (Universities, Institutes, Research centres, researchers)
Media (Magazines, newspapers, social media, blogs)
Non-technical audiences and general public impacted by developed technologies (Vulnerable Users (VU), Commuters, People with mobility challenges etc.)

During the project course, a further enrichment is envisioned, capitalising on the above categorization, including an extensive **EVENTS stakeholders' directory** based on the relevant contacts of the EVENTS consortium members, including some related projects, as well. This EVENTS stakeholders' directory will be created with a view: to get additional feedback for specific components of EVENTS project, to invite a specific group of stakeholders, in related activities, such as in knowledge transfer project events and to establish a community of supporters for the EVENTS project's areas of work. Thus, EVENTS consortium partners will be requested to provide their feedback, via using their secure networks and direct contacts, on building the preliminary EVENTS stakeholders' Directory, taking also into account the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [7, 8] and the processes, as they are described in *D.1.3: Data Management Plan*. The Directory will be included in the next version of D7.1, which is due on M18.

2.1.4 Identification of the communication content (what)

The objective of the communication and dissemination strategy is to ensure that the project developments, outcomes, and benefits are communicated in an efficient and effective way to all identified target audiences according to their unique interests and needs.

Regarding the outcomes of the project, EVENTS will promote perception and decision-making for real-time CAVs operation, by introducing nine (9) areas of work, which are the following:

1. Vehicles/Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) perception (incl. adverse weather conditions and non-standard traffic conditions and unstructured road environment);
2. Vehicles / VRUs motion prediction;
3. Optimisation-based decision-making constrained by visibility/weather conditions;
4. Perception system self-assessment;
5. Motion planning under perception uncertainty;
6. Fail-safe vehicle control/actuation;
7. High precision sensor-based localisation in adverse weather conditions;

8. Perception augmentation via Vehicle to Everything (V2X) data (Cooperative Awareness Message (CAM), VRU Awareness Message (VAM), Collective Perception Messages (CPM) integration);
9. Software Kits for closed-loop and open loop scenario-based simulation and co-simulation (incl. synthetic data generation & Safety Of The Intended Functionality (SOTIF) testing considerations);

The EVENTS areas of work have been developed since the early stages of the project, starting from the DoA as part of the overall concept of the EVENTS project and they can be summarised in six (6) main results, as follows:

- a. EVENTS enhanced perception (incl. VRUs);
- b. EVENTS robust decision-making;
- c. EVENTS perception system self-assessment;
- d. EVENTS enhanced motion planning;
- e. Scientific results;
- f. Safer, more effective, affordable and more robust CCAM;

Both the EVENTS project's areas of work and the main results (Table 3), constitute the core element for all communication and dissemination material such as brochure, banners, website and presentations. The way of communicating the EVENTS areas of work outcomes and results will evolve during the course of the project and will be based on their development and progress. In particular, the ultimate goal will be to communicate tangible benefits to the EVENTS stakeholders' community.

Table 3 EVENTS main results and areas of work

Main results	EVENTS areas of work
EVENTS enhanced perception (incl. VRUs)	1,2,4,7,8,9
EVENTS robust decision-making	3,6,9
EVENTS perception system self-assessment	4,9
EVENTS enhanced motion planning	5,6,9
Scientific results	1-9
Safer, more effective, affordable and more robust CCAM	1-9

2.1.5 Engagement plan (how)

EVENTS will follow a structured approach to precisely identify the most relevant stakeholders and target groups, their motivations for pursuing project results, and the corresponding favoured communication and dissemination approaches. More

specifically, EVENTS communication and dissemination strategy is three-fold, targeting different audiences:

- For industrial stakeholders the strategy aims at creating technical and business interest in the opportunities created by the project's results.
- For the scientific and standardisation communities the strategy aims at highlighting validated results beyond the state of the art, including results with potential for contribution to standards.
- For the wider public the strategy aims at raising awareness on research yielding interesting results, which could not have been achieved without EC funding.

The active stakeholders' engagement is part of EVENTS' overall philosophy for co-creation of knowledge and social innovation (dedicated task in WP7 – T7.4) and it is governed by five key principles of engagement: Informing (raise awareness), Consulting (share knowledge), Involving (ensure understanding), Collaborating (working in partnerships) and Empowering (placing final decisions).

The engagement plan will be supported by the identified key messages per target audience as well as by the active use of the developed communication kit and the project outreach activities, as described in the following sub-chapters and it will follow the guidelines of the developed EVENTS visual identity.

2.1.5.1 Key messages per audience

Key messages are the main points of information that EVENTS desires its interested audiences to hear, understand, and remember. They are bite-sized summations that articulate what EVENTS does, why it does it, and what value brings to stakeholders. Their purpose is not to indicate and describe a profit of EVENTS for all stakeholders (as some of them will be directly and some other indirectly affected, once the areas of work are implemented), but to describe a potential value for each stakeholder group.

Within the first months of the project and in the context of *EVENTS Communication & dissemination (T.7.1)*, **"Robust perception and decision-making for automated driving"** has been selected among the EVENTS consortium as the project's general key message (project's tagline), as a mean to indicate EVENTS' goal to spread the word about creating robust and reliable perception and decision-making systems for CAVs.

For identifying EVENTS key messages per target audience, a number of parameters have been taken into consideration, as follows:

- Raising awareness of the potential benefits of the EVENTS project's proposed technological areas of work;

- Engaging with target audiences to collect feedback for further development.
- Dissemination of project results;
- Engaging with relevant R&D projects, associations/networks, standardisation bodies and organisations to ensure knowledge exchange, interoperability and wide market penetration;
- Engaging new and final users to contribute with their input and feedback throughout the implementation of the project;
- Demonstrating how EVENTS innovations are relevant for the daily life of European citizens in the CAV area.

Key messages have been tailored for each target audience to reflect efficiently what the project intends to communicate per audience. By tailoring the messages, EVENTS team will ensure a significant impact of the diffused information and will engage the audience according to their interests and needs. The following Table 4 presents the list of key messages adapted to each one of the identified target groups.

Table 4 EVENTS key messages per stakeholder group

EVENTS stakeholders' community	Key messages
Automotive Industry (OEMs, Tier 1s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EVENTS will develop novel ML-based algorithms for accurate on-board perception.
Institutions & Committees (Policy & decision makers, Authorities in international, European and local level, Standardisation bodies)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EVENTS will provide a real-time, robust and fail-safe decision-making system, able to cope with a wide range of complex traffic scenarios (incl. VRUs, unstructured roads, adverse weather conditions).
Associations (CCAM, End-user associations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EVENTS will enhance safety in case there is a sensor malfunction or fusion outcome with low confidence.
Platforms and fora	
ICT players (ICT SMEs, Service and Technology Providers, Software Suppliers, Infrastructure Suppliers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EVENTS will create an appropriate motion planning algorithm for the CAV to be able to deal with a variety of use cases and in case of malfunction (or ODD limitation is reached) to trigger an improved Minimum Risk Manoeuvre (MRM).
Research Community (Universities, Institutes, Research centres, researchers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EVENTS will provide the research community with a solid knowledge in the area of dealing with CAV ODD limitations due to the dynamic changing road environment (VRUs, obstacles etc.) and/or due to imperfect data (e.g., sensor and communication failures). ○ EVENTS will implement and test advanced perception and decision-making

	<p>algorithms for CAVs, both in real environments and in simulation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> EVENTS is working on innovative technologies such as Novel ML-based scene recognition algorithms etc.
Media* (Magazines, newspapers, social media, blogs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EVENTS aims to communicate its outcomes to a wider European audience.
Non-technical audiences and general public impacted by developed technologies (Vulnerable Users (VU), Commuters, People with mobility challenges etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EVENTS will provide a safe and affordable perception and decision-making system for AVs to manage different kind of “events” on the horizon. EVENTS solutions will improve EU citizens everyday life.

*The role of media, in general, is to spread news around a variety of topics. EVENTS is going to create content and news around the CAVs topic and help media to fulfil their role and ‘support their existence’. Also, media are serving as a communication pipeline between all stakeholders involved.

2.1.5.2 EVENTS visual identity

EVENTS brand identity includes a manual/guide that provides a comprehensive description of its visual and verbal elements. This set of guidelines reflects project’s commitment to quality, consistency and style. EVENTS logo guidelines must be followed throughout the project runtime, to achieve the desirable uniformity and integrity of its identity and guarantee the awareness and recognition of its brand. Furthermore, these guidelines constitute a useful toolkit for the production of branded items for EVENTS, as well as for the design of its dissemination and communication material. In the following subsections, a brief description of EVENTS logo manual items is provided. EVENTS brand identity was released early in advance, on M01 (September 2022) of the project, in order to successfully fulfil its aim and commitment.

2.1.5.2.1 EVENTS Logo

- Logo description

EVENTS project aims to create a robust and resilient perception and decision-making system able to tackle complex situations, where the normal operation of the Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) is close to be disrupted (e.g., due to dynamic traffic changes, harsh weather/light conditions, unstructured road, imperfect data, sensor/communication failures, etc.). In EVENTS, in case the system or some of the subsystems cannot perform with the expected quality and reliability an improved minimum risk manoeuvre is triggered.

As a Verbal logo, on its positive format (figure 2), was created on a minimalistic design to be simple, memorable and easily adjustable in various occasions. The logotype

letters are in bold indicating its dynamics. Proposal name is accompanied by a shape which is highlighting an unsafe bended road (with a dotted line to represent the road lanes) representing the complexity of the urban environment.

Figure 2 EVENTS Logo (positive format)

EVENTS logo pack (positive format along with its negative and grayscale formats) (figure 3), has been made available for download within EVENTS website in the material hub, under the dissemination material section.

Figure 3 EVENTS Logo (negative and greyscale formats)

- Logo tagline

A memorable tagline was also developed to accompany the logo and contribute to brand association.

The selected tagline for EVENTS is the following:

Robust perception and decision-making for automated driving

EVENTS tagline is an integrant part of its communication kit and the overall Communication and Dissemination Strategy and Plan.

○ Logo fonts

The font that has been used for EVENTS logo belongs to the Montserrat fonts family (figure 4). It should be always used to all communications material and in web and media applications wherever this is possible (i.e., at the EVENTS website), to retain consistency.

Figure 4 EVENTS Logo Fonts

However, only for Microsoft (MS) templates and publication the use of Calibri (Body) font is recommended as it is friendly, easy to read, modern and clean. It is recommended to be used in all printed and digital materials (MS templates and publications, leaflets, web apps and other material) that are editable and can be publicly used in an editable format. The instructions about the recommended fonts for EVENTS material are provided in figure 5 below.

Figure 5 Fonts for EVENTS material

○ Logo Colour palette & sizes

The EVENTS logo uses three colours (figure 6):

Blue = Blue colour represents the reliability and the efficiency of the decision-making system.

Orange-Yellow = The chosen colours of yellow and orange represent the high level of risk that may be encountered due to the complex driving situations/conditions.

Figure 6 EVENTS Logo colour palette

o Logo Improper use

As regards EVENTS Logo usage (figure 7), a clear space zone around the logo has been determined to ensure the proper visibility of EVENTS logotype. Maintaining the clear space zone between the logo and other graphical elements such as typefaces, images, other logos, etc., ensures that EVENTS logo always appears unobstructed and distinctly separate from any other visuals.

A minimum size requirement was determined, in order to ensure that the logo is always clear and legible. However, when using a lower quality printing technique (i.e., screen printing), the usage of the logo in a larger size is strongly recommended.

Figure 7 EVENTS Logo Usage

Regarding the improper use, EVENTS logo, can be displayed only in the formats that are specified in the current EVENTS logo guide. EVENTS logo may not appear in any other colours than the already specified above in figure 6. It is not acceptable to rotate, skew, scale, redraw, alter or distort EVENTS logo in any way, as well as to combine EVENTS logo with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans or symbols (figure 8).

Figure 8 EVENTS Logo improper use

- Logo usage on social media

EVENTS Logo on social media should be only used in a white background (figure 9).

Figure 9 EVENTS Logo usage on social media

- Logo usage on backgrounds

Concerning EVENTS Logo usage on backgrounds (figure 10), it should be noted, that, when placing the logo on an image, colour or pattern, it is essential that there is enough contrast between the logo and the background. The logo must not be placed on backgrounds that distract from or compete with the logo.

Figure 10 EVENTS Logo Usage on backgrounds

2.1.5.2.2 Templates

In the context of EVENTS consistent brand identity, MS office templates both for project presentations (figure 11) and deliverables (figure 12) have been created, since M01, in line with the given brand guidelines. Having unified templates, the project can streamline its processes and improve its coherence. The Deliverable template contains all the necessary information about the metadata of each produced document. The presentation template contains a set of suitable graphics, in order to illustrate the contexts, the objectives, the timeline, relative figures and data. Partners have been kindly requested to make proper use of both templates and to ensure their professional use in line with the already defined aesthetic criteria. Project templates are available within the project’s internal repository.

Figure 11 EVENTS Power Point presentation template

**Reliable in-Vehicle pErception and decisioN-making in
complex environmenTal conditionS**

Grant Agreement Number: 101069614

D.x.x: Title must be placed here

Document Identification			
Status	Draft	Due Date	Monday, 05 September 2022
Version	0.1	Submission Date	
Related WP	WPx	Document Reference	D.x.x
Related Deliverable(s)	Insert Related Deliverables	Dissemination Level	PU/SEN
Lead Participant	Insert Lead Participant (partner short name)	Document Type:	R/DEM/DEC/Other/ETHICS/CRDP/DATA
Contributors	Insert Contributors (partners short name)	Lead Author	Insert Author (first name, last name)
		Reviewers	Insert 1 st reviewer (first name, last name, company) Insert 2 nd reviewer (first name, last name, company)

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Figure 12 Cover page of EVENTS Deliverable template

2.1.5.3 Communication Kit (Channels, Tools & Means)

A variety of channels will be actively used, to effectively flow EVENTS information, create awareness and reach out to the targeted audiences, by taking into consideration the specific characteristics and needs of each targeted group. The following indicative list of proposed communication channels, tools and means shows the already defined kit of transmitting the information produced within EVENTS project. This list is subject to further updates during the project lifetime and based on its emerging needs.

2.1.5.3.1 Online Channels

The EVENTS project online channels include the Project's website and the social media accounts.

- Project website

EVENTS website constitutes the backbone of the project's communication and dissemination activities. The website serves for all different users and stakeholders and provides up-to-date information in a simple way about the project objectives, the proposed areas of work, the use cases, the consortium, project results, related articles and project material (e.g., public deliverables, open access publications, newsletters,

dissemination & presentation material, news etc.). The website was officially launched on M01 (September 2022) and became fully functional, in its current view, on M03 (November 2022) (figures 13 & 14), including several sections, as detailed described below. It can be accessed through the following URL: <https://www.events-project.eu/>.

Figure 13 EVENTS Website main page

Figure 14 EVENTS Website main page

The website's content is organized in five sections:

1. **Home:** This section serves as the cover page/homepage of EVENTS website, including information about the project's idea, the use cases, the main project facts (project number, call identifier, topic, duration), and displays the most recent conducted events. Additionally, it contains information about the EVENTS consortium team and recent updates from the EVENTS twitter account.
2. **About EVENTS:** This section provides detailed information about the project's scope, its objectives and impact and the project's use cases.
3. **Consortium:** In this area, a description of each EVENTS' partners, as well as of the people involved per entity, is given, to highlight the consortium competencies in fulfilling the project objectives.
4. **Material Hub:** This section acts as a repository and includes the project deliverables, publications (e.g., partner's presentations from conferences, scientific papers etc.), dissemination material (e.g., EVENTS logo pack, leaflet, poster, roll-up etc.), the press clippings from the partners' media presence, the produced e-newsletters and finally any audio-visual material, as well as the organised webinars/workshops that are being developed and conducted, correspondingly, during the project's lifetime (figure 15).

Figure 15 EVENTS Website Material Hub

5. **News:** In this area the most recent project news and updates, related to the project are announced. The attendance in events/conferences/clustering activities is also mentioned here both for past and forthcoming events (figure 16).

Figure 16 EVENTS Website News section

The footer of the EVENTS website, in all pages, includes the newsletter subscription functionality, the funding acknowledgment text, the EU emblem and the website's imprint along with contact details for any interested audience (figure 17).

Figure 17 EVENTS Website footer

EVENTS website is frequently updated and it will provide all recent information on the evolution of the project, including information about project results and outcomes, the use cases, as well as the communication and dissemination activities within EVENTS. The material hub remains also continuously updated with any corresponding material that derives from the partner's activities. It will be maintained for five years after the project completion, to provide information about the project deliverables, results and outcomes to any interested party. Last but not least, EVENTS website is linked to all EVENTS social media accounts.

- [Social Media accounts](#)

EVENTS, along with the website launching, is maintaining before the beginning of the project on M01 (September 2022), three social media accounts on Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube respectively, in order to maximize dissemination of the project results and engagement. All social media accounts have been developed and maintained by SEAB. In the same context, SEAB is envisage to develop, also, an account for EVENTS project in the OpenAIRE repository by M12.

EVENTS Twitter account (figure 18) has been created to raise awareness of the project, especially for the wider Cooperative, connected and automated mobility community and it has been created at the very early stages of the project (June 2022). The language of the account is English, however, occasional posts in other languages are encouraged and made when needed. EVENTS twitter account can be accessed in the following link: <https://twitter.com/EVENTSproject22>.

Figure 18 EVENTS Twitter front page

This account is used for presenting the latest news about the project with updates and pictures from meetings, workshops, events etc., with direct links to the project material as well as retweets from related twitter accounts of initiatives, partners, and similar projects. SEAB oversees the daily management of this account. Besides, all EVENTS partners are responsible for increasing the awareness of this tool, by creating linkages to their accounts and by providing SEAB with relevant content and contributions related to their achievements.

The EVENTS LinkedIn account (figure 19) has been also set up well in advance on June 2022, to attract interested stakeholders and interact with them. The language of LinkedIn page is English, however, occasional posts in other languages are also encouraged when needed. The goal of this tool is to share content and connect with already established interested groups and transmit the project's insights, concept and vision. EVENTS LinkedIn page account can be accessed here: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eventsproject22/>.

Figure 19 EVENTS LinkedIn front page

EVENTS project maintains, also, a channel on YouTube (figure 20), aiming at sharing videos related to the project achievements, in the context of its dissemination and communication procedures. YouTube is considered a valuable channel for showcasing the project's general video, the project's use cases, as well as other audio visual activities (e.g., EVENTS partners interview series). EVENTS YouTube account can be accessed here: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCAgJLY4iE7y0gw8GntHhIqW>.

Figure 20 EVENTS YouTube channel front page

2.1.5.3.2 Dissemination Tools

EVENTS’s dissemination tools, either in hard copy or in digital/electronic format, are in line with the overall EVENTS communication strategy to ensure the achievement of the project’s objectives and the effective engagement of the interested target audiences. Such material is always consistent with EVENTS brand identity and the communication guidelines provided by the European Commission (EC) [1].

Dissemination tools, as part of the project’s communication kit, will be updated as necessary throughout the course of the project, in order to include EVENTS achievements, findings and outcomes. The dissemination process is a responsibility of all EVENTS work packages (WPs) under the lead of the Communication manager SEAB. The project’s dissemination tools consist of: i) the project’s fact sheet, ii) the overall presentation, iii) the brochure, iv) the poster, v) the roll up banner and vi) the project video.

According to EC instructions, all recipients of EU funds have the legal obligation to explicitly acknowledge that their action has received EU funding. This requirement is to ensure visibility and transparency. The obligation requires all beneficiaries of EU funding to acknowledge the support from the European Union (EU) on all communication materials. An important element with this regard is the European Union emblem and the funding statement, which must be displayed prominently on all printed and digital products, websites, social media channels and other communication products [1], as stipulated in the articles 16.3 and 17 of EVENTS Grant Agreement. As a matter of fact, all dissemination tools have and will acknowledge the EU funding following the abovementioned instructions.

- EVENTS factsheet

EVENTS fact sheet has been prepared, since M01 (September 2022), to provide a complete overview of the project details (figure 21). It outlines all the necessary baseline information related to the project identification and can be used by EVENTS consortium in their communication channels, as a complete description of the project.

EVENTS fact sheet has been made available through EVENTS website, in the material hub, under the dissemination material section.

FACT SHEET

ReliE in-Vehide pErception and decisioN-making in complex environmenTal conditiO5

At a glance

Full Title: ReliE in-Vehide pErception and decisioN-making in complex environmenTal conditiO5

Project ID: 101069614

Funded under: Horizon Europe

Funding scheme: IA –Innovation Action

Duration: 36 months
01 September 2022 – 31 August 2025

Total cost: EUR 6.520.598

EU contribution: EUR 5.534.448

Call: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01

Topic: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-01

Coordinated by: Institute of Communication & Computer Systems (ICCS)

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 EVENTS Project

Consortium

Description

EVENTS is a Horizon Europe project that brings together a complementary consortium of 11 partners from 7 EU countries and UK, with the view to deal with complex situations where the normal operation of the Connected and Automated Vehicle (CAV) is close to be disrupted (e.g., due to dynamic traffic changes, harsh weather/light conditions, unstructured road, imperfect data, sensor/communication failures, etc.).

These situations are called “events” and they are creating challenges for CAVs, that should be overcome in order to enable safe and reliable automated driving in such cases. An indicative, but non-exhaustive list of these challenges is the following:

- Perception in complex urban environments, in particular dealing with Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs);
- Perception in adverse weather and poor lighting conditions;
- Perception under (partial) occlusions;
- Accurate prediction of road user trajectory (especially if highly manoeuvrable, like VRUs);
- Utilisation of connectivity (off-board information) to improve accuracy, certainty & reliability of perception;
- Reduction of the costs of the required sensor-suites;
- Real-time decision-making and motion planning especially in uncertain situations;
- Self-assessment of perception systems.

EVENTS project aims to create a robust and resilient perception and decision-making system, able to tackle the abovementioned challenges. In EVENTS, in case the system or some of the subsystems cannot perform with the expected quality and reliability, an improved minimum risk manoeuvre is triggered. Within the scope of EVENTS project, and in order to cover a wide area of scenarios, the various types of “events” are clustered under three main use cases:

- Interaction with VRUs in Complex Urban Environment;
- Non-Standard and Unstructured Road Conditions;
- Low Visibility and Adverse Weather Conditions.

To achieve its objectives, EVENTS will bring together, adapt and improve technological advances, in perception and decision-making for real-time CAVs operation. As a summary, the major expected breakthroughs to be introduced by EVENTS project, are the following: i) the robust and reliable perception of objects, and especially VRUs, under complex urban traffic and bad weather or low visibility conditions, ii) the improved perception performance while using cost-efficient sensor suites and iii) the real-time decision-making for CAVs under non-standard traffic and unstructured road conditions.

Funded by the European Union

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Figure 21 EVENTS Fact sheet

○ EVENTS Standard Presentation

EVENTS standard presentation (figure 22) has been prepared within M03 of the project with a twofold purpose. On the one hand, it provides a more detailed, ready-to-present overview of the project than the one used in the rest of the dissemination material (towards providing in detail EVENTS objectives and highlighting the project's use cases and impact) and on the other hand, it can be used by the consortium partners without any prior content approval in related events, for presenting EVENTS. It follows the guidelines stemming from EVENTS brand identity and it is also available in EVENTS website, in the material hub, under the dissemination material section.

Figure 22 EVENTS Standard Presentation

○ EVENTS Brochure

EVENTS brochure's design is presented in a roll fold leaflet, where each page folds in on itself, representing a twofold leaflet in a size of a half of A4 leaflet, aiming to provide an overview of EVENTS project via a set of images, graphics and text (figures 23 & 24). More specifically, the leaflet provides at a glance information about the project's vision and presents the three use cases, as well as the project's wider impact. EVENTS concept image is also displayed within the brochure. The consortium partners' logos, as well as general information about the project are displayed in the last and the cover pages of the brochure. EVENTS brochure has been developed following the project's brand identity and in line with the other communication material, tools and channels such as the project's website, poster and roll-up.

The main objective of this material is to be distributed during EVENTS activities (use cases, knowledge transfer events etc.), at exterior workshops, conferences, trade fairs and exhibitions. The first version has been launched on M06 (February 2023) and has been made available within EVENTS website, in the project material hub, under the dissemination material section.

EVENTS is envisaged to produce an update, during the project course and based on the project’s needs. SEAB is responsible for providing the design of the leaflets to the partners, as well as printing copies according to the project needs and budget availability and constraints.

Figure 23 EVENTS Brochure (cover and last pages)

Figure 24 EVENTS Brochure (inner pages)

○ EVENTS Roll-up banner

A set of 2 roll-up banners will be produced for disseminating the project’s outcomes at specific events, such as exterior workshops, conferences, exhibitions, knowledge transfer events, EVENTS Summer School, and at the project’s Final Event. The first EVENTS roll-up banner (figure 25) has been developed since M03 (November 2022) of the project. It presents the project’s vision and main facts and displays the consortium partners’ logos. An updated version of the roll-up banner will be produced within the project’s lifetime based on the use cases activities and their outcomes, in order to be distributed at congresses, workshops, exhibitions, fairs and other events.

EVENTS roll-up banner has been made available within EVENTS website, in the project material hub, under the dissemination material section.

Figure 25 EVENTS Roll up banner

○ EVENTS Poster

EVENTS poster has been made available since M06 (February 2023) and has been produced according to the partners’ needs during the project’s runtime. EVENTS poster follows the consistency guidelines of the project brand identity, towards respecting the proper use of the project logo (figure 26). It aims to facilitate and foster the project’s scientific outreach in related events, conferences, workshops, exhibitions etc. Moreover, it provides at a glance, information about the project’s vision and objectives, analyses the project’s concept and shortly presents the three use cases and the project’s expected impact. The consortium partners’ logos, as well as general information about the project are displayed at the bottom of the poster.

An updated version of the poster will be produced within the project’s lifetime based on the use cases activities and their outcomes, in order to be distributed at congresses, workshops, exhibitions, fairs and other events. EVENTS poster has been made available within the project website, in the material hub, under the dissemination material section.

Figure 26 EVENTS Poster

- [EVENTS official project video](#)

EVENTS general video is planned to be officially launched on M18 with the aim to gain more attention and spread significant awareness on the project activities. The plan is to develop a 3 to 4 minutes' video that would make use of visual, sound and text elements to introduce the project and visually explains the project's concept to non-technical audiences and the general public. This general video will remark the project's vision and objectives, its concept, the use cases, as well as the expected project impact. The project video will be produced in English and it will be disseminated via EVENTS social media, as well as it will be posted in the project's website and uploaded on EVENTS YouTube channel. It is expected to be disseminated by all project partners, using various means of dissemination.

2.1.5.3.3 [Means](#)

- [EVENTS newsletters](#)

EVENTS newsletters will be sent out to various users' groups (e.g., professional associations, end user communities etc.) via social media and direct emailing. EVENTS' website visitors have the opportunity to sign up to EVENTS e-newsletter, using the corresponding subscription functionality, which provides regular updates, develops EVENTS profile, and achieves wider stakeholder recognition.

EVENTS e-newsletters will constitute an electronic means of distributing project findings and news, implemented activities, as well as upcoming actions. The content of the e-newsletters is based on the continuous progress of the project and aims to inform the interested audience about the key outcomes and advances of the project, while ensuring conformance with GDPR.

Eight e-newsletters have been planned within the project course, starting from M06. The 1st EVENTS e-newsletter is planned to be released at the beginning of March 2023, to include all project activities, within the first six months of the project course.

Upon their creation and distribution, all e-newsletters will be available through EVENTS website, in the material hub, under the newsletter section.

- [EVENTS partners interview series](#)

EVENTS partners interview series will be designed and released at the end of the first project year (M12) for reaching out targeted groups of relevant stakeholders and raising awareness on the activities each partner is involved.

2.1.5.4 EVENTS Outreach activities

Within the project duration two EVENTS knowledge transfer events, two webinars, three use cases demos, a Summer School and a Final event will be planned, organized and conducted, to support project activities, developments and the overall outreach.

More in detail, **two knowledge transfer events** either in form of focus groups or in form of specialised workshops will be organized in the beginning (M10) and the end of the project (M32), in the context of task 7.2 activities, to actively support the commencement as well as the validity of the exploitation and business exploration processes.

Also, due to the industrial nature of the project and for promoting gender equality in research and innovation the focus on the gender equality is oriented on the participating partners and the difference they can make within their communities. **A dedicated Summer School** will be organised on M30 to promote the entrance and familiarisation of university female researchers and students in the technical/scientific fields covered by EVENTS.

In addition, **the organisation of two promotional webinars** (around major project milestones) is planned for the female students at High Scientific Schools, for stimulating their interest and paving their way for their educational opportunities, related to EVENTS technical topics.

It is, also, worth mentioning, that during the lifetime of the project, demonstration events will be held for each of the **three EVENTS Use Cases** with the main objective to showcase the EVENTS system to the members of the Advisory board and to any other interested member of the broader stakeholder community, such as relevant authorities and standardisation bodies, end user communities, related industries, researchers, academics and any other interested persons. One of the basic objectives of the EVENTS demonstration events is to collect appropriate feedback on the developed technologies, identify any weaknesses of the proposed EVENTS' developments and address them efficiently. Those activities are also considered critical to promote the benefits from the usage of the EVENTS system to related industries and ensure wide market penetration.

A core dissemination activity of the EVENTS consortium is also **the organisation of a Final Event** to be held towards the project end. During this Conference the EVENTS results will be thoroughly presented through technical presentations and live demonstrations to a large number of stakeholders (more than 120 experts). To ensure wide outreach, the final event's technical presentations, performed discussions and other presented material will be available at a dedicated prominent section in the EVENTS website.

2.1.6 Roadmap, timeline and action plan

EVENTS approach to communication has been built following a three-phase approach based on the process of developments and the availability of tangible results from its research activities. More specifically, Phase 1 “Initial awareness” starts on M01 and lasts till M12, where WP2 activities in relation to the Use cases, requirements and system design are expected to be finalised. Phase 2 “Targeted awareness” starts on M13 and lasts till M30, where WP3-WP5 activities related to the perception and self-assessment, on-board decision making for fail-safe vehicle motion and system integration and safety compliance are expected to be finalised. Last but not least, phase 3 “Strategic phase” runs from M31 till the project end and beyond.

According to communication roadmap, as it is presented below in table 5, each phase includes targeted activities, as well as, related channels, tools and means, which will foster the communication and dissemination of the respective key messages and information as well as the transmission of the available project results to the target audiences.

Table 5 EVENTS communication roadmap and timeline

Project Phase	Activities	Channels
Phase 1 – “Initial awareness” (M1-M12)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Agree upon the EVENTS communication and dissemination and social awareness strategy & future communication and dissemination and social awareness activities. ○ Create initial awareness in markets related to the project’s scope and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Website ○ Social media ○ Press activities ○ E-newsletters ○ Printed material ○ Communication campaign ○ Conferences’ presentations ○ Knowledge transfer events
Phase 2 – “Targeted awareness” (M13-M30)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Create more “<i>targeted awareness</i>” regarding EVENTS areas of work with targeted stakeholder groups. ○ Inform the target audiences and market about the technological breakthroughs and business benefits (including early results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Website ○ Social media ○ Press activities ○ Webinars, workshops etc. ○ E-newsletters ○ Printed material ○ Project video ○ Journal papers ○ Conferences’ presentations ○ Communication campaign ○ Knowledge transfer events

	from use cases assessment).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Summer School
Phase 3 – “Strategic phase” (M31-M36+beyond)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Maximize target market and industry awareness regarding the EVENTS outputs and its exploitable products. ○ Support project sustainability and effective exploitation and market penetration and replication. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Website ○ Social media ○ Press ○ Webinars, workshops etc ○ E-newsletters ○ Printed material ○ Project video ○ Journal papers ○ Conferences’ presentations ○ Use Case demos ○ Knowledge transfer events ○ Summer School ○ Final event

2.2 Communication & Dissemination procedures

As part of the activities to be implemented within Task 7.1, as well as in WP7 in general, in order to guarantee, verify and produce high quality publications, presentations and other communication and dissemination material, as well as to avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted and/or confidential information and to monitor and record, effectively and efficiently, the project’s dissemination activities, a set of communication and dissemination procedures have been established.

EVENTS communication and dissemination procedures include guidelines and set out the main steps to be followed by partners for the publication or presentation of the work done within the framework of the EVENTS project. The full description of the communication/dissemination procedures for EVENTS is available through an online excel spreadsheet, which has been circulated and made available among the EVENTS consortium since the early stages of the project (right after EVENTS kick-off meeting). There have been also made available in the Annex 1 of the present document.

3. EVENTS scientific approach

3.1 Publications

EVENTS will draft scientific publications and other contributions for the technical literature and dedicated high impact journals, in order to share the project's progress and outcomes with scientific community. The ultimate goal of scientific publications within EVENTS, is to enrich science by publishing original empirical and theoretical work developed within the project. The term scientific publication within EVENTS is simple referring to one of the following types of publications:

- *Conference papers*, which are usually reviewed during a specific period and authors receive their acceptance or rejection notifications at the same time. Conference papers are usually short and concise with a limitation on the number of pages allowed.
- *Journal papers*, where the time required for publication is very flexible. The revision process required for a journal paper undergoes a very meticulous and thorough peer-review process, which is far more detailed than conference revisions, and may take a substantial period of time.

Journals as well as conference proceedings are considered as key pipelines for EVENTS scientific dissemination. EVENTS will guarantee open access (following the GA guidelines of the Annex 5: Article 17) to every EVENTS publication (towards sustaining also either self-archiving / 'green' open access or open access publishing / 'gold' open access for both the publication itself and its metadata) and this will be ensured for all interested stakeholder communities, mainly through the project's public gateways (EVENTS online channels) and through the use of the EU innovative open access publishing services (e.g., Open Research Europe (ORE) Platform, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), OpenAIRE etc.). These services will assist the EVENTS partners to overcome difficulties that arise from obstacles towards open access of project's results that occur from publishers' policy (e.g., embargo period).

EVENTS communication team has already created an indicative list (calendar) of relevant scientific journals, to facilitate partners towards the submission of scientific papers, which can be found within Annex 2 of the current document.

EVENTS will consider a complementary set of parameters prior to any publication, in order to improve the outreach and the visibility of the project and to maintain the highest standard for scientific publications. These parameters include: the access modality (target mainly open access publishing houses), article processing charges and conference fees (to be covered accordingly by each participating partner), indexing and conference rank, research integrity (for content verification and plagiarism

avoidance), management of IPR (according to the EVENTS Consortium Agreement (CA) and GA).

3.2 Participation in Events and Conferences

One of the project's significant dissemination activities will be the consortium participation (physical or virtual) in external conferences, workshops, seminar, webinars and other third-party events via presentations. Additionally, project's presence in trade fairs and exhibitions is foreseen. The main aim of this practice is to raise awareness about the project, inform about its offered solution and disseminate its produced results within the scientific and technology community, businesses, end users, public authorities, policy makers, associations etc. From the beginning of the project a calendar of upcoming events and conferences that are considered as valuable opportunities for the project has been created and is regularly updated mainly by WP7 team and by the consortium partners. EVENTS partners are regularly informed through monthly emails about upcoming key opportunities, so they will be able to benefit from them. The calendar can be found in Annex 3 of the current document.

4. EVENTS Clustering & Networking activities

EVENTS will perform, throughout the project duration, international networking activities to exploit potential synergies with pertinent EU projects, organisations and networks.

4.1 Clustering activities with EU projects

EVENTS consortium will coordinate with other relevant actors and build on top of existing national and European projects and initiatives. Possible collaboration in joint workshops or other activities and events (e.g., webinars, exhibition stands) will be sought wherever possible. EVENTS will invite members of projects as speakers in related special interested sessions, webinars, workshops and other events and activities, organised by the project, in order to discuss and provide their valuable insights in the area of CCAM, as well as, on Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs). Moreover, the project will seek to participate in related projects' events with the aim to present the project's approach, key assets and outcomes and to have an exchange of views in common research fields.

4.1.1 Joint Communication and Dissemination Activities with sister projects

The establishment of possible collaborations in joint workshops, webinars and other events and activities will be sought within -but not limited to- the related projects that are initially and indicatively listed and described below in table 6. This list will be enhanced and be kept up-to-date during the project course.

ROADVIEW project is funded under the same topic with EVENTS, namely the *HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-01: More powerful and reliable on-board perception and decision-making technologies addressing complex environmental conditions (CCAM Partnership)*.

The main scope of this topic was to achieve a secure and trustworthy interaction between vehicles, infrastructure and road users, robust (e.g., weather resilient) and accurate on-board environment positioning and perception systems are essential for the extraction of reliable information required for real-time driving decision-making.

Additionally, effort is also focused on creating synergies with other related EU funded projects (like CONNECT, FAME, SUNRISE, SINFONICA, AUGMENTED CCAM, PoDIUM), which are funded under complementary to EVENTS topics, namely the topics HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-04, HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-06, HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-02, HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-05, HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01-03.

Table 6 Clustering projects

Project Name	Description
<p>ROADVIEW: Robust Automated Driving in Extreme Weather</p>	<p>ROADVIEW is an EU-funded Horizon Europe Innovation Action aiming to develop robust and cost-efficient in-vehicle perception and decision-making systems for connected and automated vehicles with enhanced performance under harsh weather conditions and different traffic scenarios (https://roadview-project.eu/).</p>
<p>CONNECT: Continuous and Efficient Cooperative Trust Management for Resilient CCAM</p>	<p>The vision of the project is to address the convergence of security and safety in CCAM by assessing dynamic trust relationships and defining a trust model and trust reasoning framework based on which involved entities can establish trust for cooperatively executing safety-critical functions. The CONNECT Trust Management framework is the basis that models and captures the trust relationships of the next generation CCAM systems. CONNECT's new safety paradigm is a key element in bringing autonomous driving to a completely new level of trustworthiness and is expected to lead to long-term consumer acceptance as a result (https://horizon-connect.eu/).</p>
<p>FAME: Framework for coordination of Automated Mobility in Europe</p>	<p>FAME will develop and validate common methodologies and tools to facilitate the sharing of best practices and lessons learned to support the collaboration within the community of CCAM stakeholders across the complex cross-sectorial value chain needed for the organisation and evaluation of large-scale demonstration and future scale-up to the impacts of complete CCAM solutions (https://www.connectedautomateddriving.eu/).</p>
<p>SUNRISE: Safety assurance framework for connected, automated mobility Systems</p>	<p>The SUNRISE project is about safety assurance of Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) systems. This safety assurance is crucial for their successful adoption and deployment in society. CCAM systems must be reliable in every possible driving scenario. This requires a strong safety argumentation, which remains a significant challenge worldwide. Several initiatives have started to develop test- and assessment methods for CCAM systems, applying a scenario-based approach, and combining both physical and virtual testing. Although automotive stakeholders generally seem to agree on this overall approach, the current situation is leading to silo solutions. The lack of a common approach,</p>

	<p>therefore hampers the large-scale and safe introduction of CCAM systems in society (https://ccam-sunrise-project.eu/)</p>
<p>SINFONICA: Social INnovation to FOster iNclusve Cooperative, connected and Automated mobility</p>	<p>SINFONICA aims to develop functional, efficient, and innovative strategies, methods and tools to engage CCAM users, providers and other stakeholders (i.e., citizens, including vulnerable users, transport operators, public administrations, service providers, researchers, vehicle and technology suppliers) to collect, understand and structure in a manageable and exploitable way their needs, desires, and concerns related to CCAM. SINFONICA will co-create final decision support tools for designers and decision makers to enhance the CCAM seamless and sustainable deployment, to be inclusive and equitable for all citizens (https://sinfonica.eu/).</p>
<p>AUGMENTED CCAM: Augmenting and Evaluating the Physical and Digital Infrastructure for CCAM deployment</p>	<p>Physical and digital infrastructure (PDI) represents a key resource for enabling and supporting the integration of vehicles into the whole transport system. The EU-funded AUGMENTED CCAM project intends to understand, harmonise and assess adapted and innovative PDI support solutions. Eleven such solutions will be developed and tested in various PDI scenarios. This will allow for the assessment of different PDI support solutions, including on the safety of the entire transport infrastructure, traffic safety and efficiency, driving behaviour, and the environmental footprint, as well as service reliability, trust and security. Overall, the project’s goal is to speed up the large-scale operation of cooperative, connected and automated mobility solutions for all actors (https://augmentedccam.com/).</p>
<p>PoDIUM: PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM</p>	<p>The EU-funded PoDIUM project aims to identify and assess the connectivity and cooperation enablers to achieve higher levels of automation. Use of a multi-connectivity approach and a distributed, interoperable, hybrid data management environment will advance important PDI technologies. PoDIUM's final outcome will be a reference architecture that can be applied to various road environments and infrastructure equipment (https://podium-project.eu).</p>

The establishment of clustering activities between EVENTS sister projects is imperative for the successful outreach of their results and outcomes and thus is guided by the following objectives:

- Engagement in collaborative work in order to maximize the impact of the communication and dissemination of results amongst the relevant stakeholders.
- Exchange of technical information between the projects, leading to a stronger, more accurate and aligned vision of this clustering network.
- Contribution to the dissemination of top-level, high-quality EU funding programmes and support European Research and Innovation Actions.
- Fulfilment of the European Commission’s expectation of an integrated collaborative approach between Horizon Europe projects.

At this point, it is worth mentioning that EVENTS has, already, established liaison with the projects FAME and ROADVIEW. As regards FAME, EVENTS has been invited to be registered in FAME’s Knowledge Base, as a key action towards supporting the CCAM Partnership. As regards ROADVIEW, a special interested session was jointly submitted with EVENTS, to the upcoming ITS Europe 2023.

4.2 EVENTS Networking activities with EU and international organisations

EVENTS partners will seize every opportunity to discuss EVENTS developments within related organisations, associations and networks, where, they already participate, and, also, to present technical advances in respective technical meetings and fora. Networking with relevant associations, organisations and European R&D initiatives, in both European and International level, is very important since this will ensure knowledge interchange between key actors and the adoption of proposed solutions.

EVENTS will start disseminating its assets, share knowledge and experience and mutually liaising with the following -but not limited to- key actors, based on its teams’ regular and frequent collaboration with them (all the below actors, as stipulated in table 7, will be part of the upcoming EVENTS Stakeholders’ Directory, which is going to be, also, enriched with the members of the EVENTS Advisory Board:

Table 7 Networking EU and international organisations

EVENTS stakeholders’ community	EVENTS stakeholder’s Directory
Automotive Industry (OEMs, Tier 1s)	TOYOTA Belgium (LoI), EUCAR, CLEPA, BOSCH
Institutions & Committees (Policy & decision makers, Authorities in international, European and local level, Standardisation bodies)	TRB council, JARI Japan Automobile Research Institute, European ITS Committee, ISO, Association for Standardization of Automation and Measuring Systems (ASAM), SAE, FRAV, VMAD, ETSI Technical Committees

Associations (CCAM, End-user associations)	CCAM EU partnership, ERTICO
Platforms and fora	ERTRAC WG on Connectivity and Automated Driving, Horizon Results Platform, Intelligent Move network
ICT players (ICT SMEs, Service and Technology Providers, Software Suppliers, Infrastructure Suppliers)	Epos Sintering
Research Community (Universities, Institutes, Research centres, researchers)	EARPA
Media (Magazines, newspapers, social media, blogs)	EVENTS LinkedIn & twitter accounts, CINEA social media
Non-technical audiences and general public impacted by developed technologies (Vulnerable Users, Commuters, People with mobility challenges etc.)	General public in the countries, where EVENTS partners are based

The aforementioned list will be part of the forthcoming EVENTS stakeholders' Directory and it will be extended during the project course based on the needs that will arise from the project developments and outcomes. Some of the above-mentioned actors will also be invited to participate in EVENTS Advisory Board, which is currently under formulation.

5. EVENTS Social awareness

5.1 Directions to social innovation

EVENTS, as part of its social innovation perspective, will thoroughly investigate possible ways to achieve its full potential and to benefit society. Social innovation in WP7 is inherently fed into EVENTS work plan, ensuring that societal aspects are always considered. More specifically, this will be achieved through EVENTS Task 7.4 on Social innovation & Gender Equality, which is going to be run during the last year of the project course (M24-M36).

According to Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), *“Social innovation refers to the design and implementation of new solutions that imply conceptual, process, product, or organisational change, which ultimately aim to improve the welfare and wellbeing of individuals and communities...To fully tap the potential of social innovation, an enabling policy framework is needed to support public, non-profit and private actors to co-construct and implement socially innovative solutions ...”* [10]. In addition, according to Chapter 3 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights [9], the rights to equality before the law, to non-discrimination, to cultural, religious and linguistic diversity, to equality between women and men, to the rights of the child, to the rights of the elderly and to the integrations of persons with disabilities are governed by the articles 20-26.

Capitalising on both the definition of the social innovation term and the aforementioned consensus of rights to equity, future developed CCAM systems must also follow, comply and take into consideration these rights and aspects, otherwise they may create the breeding ground to social inequality and several social disparities, including social exclusion.

As a matter of fact, in order to ensure the effective adoption of the CCAM systems in general and for autonomous vehicles to become successfully socially integrated, in particular, as well as to achieve a better understanding of the CCAM science - society relationship, EVENTS, through Task 7.4, will provide the conceptual directions through an exploration of methods/approaches for matching the short- and long-term social mobility needs with EVENTS system, based also on the three developed use cases.

These mobility needs will be based on the ones derive from the transportation literature [11] and are named as: The Availability, the Accessibility, the Affordability, and the Acceptability need. As part of the use cases, different groups will be also taken into consideration in the research, such as -but not limited to- the elderly, people with disabilities, young people (and children), digitally non-connected people, low income and unemployed people etc. As part of this work, social innovation pathways will be exploited at different levels (local, regional, national, European) and sectors (public,

private, civil). The conducted research and the corresponding results and outcomes will be documented in the last update of D7.1 (M36).

5.2 Approach to gender equality

EVENTS gender mainstreaming is primarily ruled by the article 4 of the Annex 5 of the EVENTS GA, where it is mentioned that *“The beneficiaries must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action and, where applicable, in line with the gender equality plan. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level”*.

The treatment of the gender dimension in all aspects of EVENTS will incorporate the objectives of the Commission’s Gender Equality Strategy for 2020-2025 (COM/2020/152 final) [12]. Gender dimension will be considered in the different proposed activities. EVENTS technical innovations and use cases are gender agnostic, since they address researchers and road users, in general. For example, VRUs that our research targets will be sex-agnostic, any motion planning for VRUs will incorporate equal gender data, any models used for training will be also gender neutral and so on. Moreover, all engagement and demonstration activities will pay special attention to gender balance and the participation of women and non-binary individuals will be assessed. Also, any presentations, publications, and reports will avoid gender-biased language and examples. In general, the institutions/organizations included in the consortium are aligned and follow EU Commission’s guidelines that guarantee and promote gender equality in research and innovation. Some of the measures carried out by the respective institutions are: boosting and increasing all genders participation in research, development and innovation, promoting gender equality and stimulating the excellence of all genders in research.

Towards the direction of gender neutrality and equality, and the lack of work-life balance and opportunities in the automotive industry, which are considered as significant barriers for women [13], EVENTS has dedicated a specific task (T7.4) to actively support the amplification of a gender-diverse workforce in the automotive industry. To this end, a dedicated to female researchers Summer School is envisaged to be organised within EVENTS duration, to promote the entrance and familiarisation of university female researchers and students in the technical/scientific fields covered by EVENTS. In addition, the organisation and conduction of promotional webinars is, also, planned for female students of High Scientific Schools, for stimulating their interest and paving their way for their educational opportunities, related to EVENTS’ technical topics. Overall, each EVENTS partner is expected to make strong commitments to gender equality – both transparency and workplace equality. The conducted activities and their results will be documented in the last update of D7.1 (M36).

6. EVENTS Communication & Dissemination Activities

6.1 Conducted activities

The activities that have been performed during the first six months (M01-M06) of EVENTS implementation are listed in tables 8 to 11 below:

- Conference attendance

Table 8 EVENTS attended conferences between M01-M06

Date	Event	Location	Title of presentation	Involved partners	Description (if available)/url
25/10/2022	Connected, Cooperative & Automated mobility (CCAM) event	Brussels, Belgium	EVENTS project on CCAM	ICCS	Presentation was focused on highlighting the key facts, objectives and impact of EVENTS project, and how the project is linked to the CCAM Partnership's Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). https://www.events-project.eu/news-title-1/

- Exhibitions/Booths

Table 9 EVENTS attended exhibitions between M01-M06

Date	Exhibition (E)/ Booth (B)	Event	Partners Involved	Description	Announcement
07-08/12/2022	Booth	8th ITS Hellas Conference	SEAB	SEAB showcased EVENTS in its booth	https://www.events-project.eu/8th-its-hellas-conference-07-08-12-2022/
15/02/2023	Booth	RTR conference 2023	ICCS	EVENTS networking at EC Stand	https://www.events-project.eu/events-networking-at-ec-stand-in-rtr-2023-14-16-02-2023/

- Press Clippings

Table 10 EVENTS press activities between M01-M06

Type of activity	Title of publication	Date	Involved partners	Press Clippings
EVENTS kick-off press release	SEAbility participated in EVENTS Kick-Off meeting	September 2022	SEAB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://seability.eu/2022/09/09/events-kick-off-meeting-in-athens/
EVENTS kick-off press release	EVENTS: a new HORIZON project officially launched	September 2022	ICCS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://i-sense.iccs.gr/news/14382/
EVENTS kick-off press release	ICCS & SEAB participate in EVENTS project	November 2022	ICCS/ SEAB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.kathimerini.gr/society/562118311/ochimata-choris-odigo-ena-vima-pio-konta-me-ti-symvoli-toy-emp/ ○ https://www.eea.gr/arthra-eea/events-aytomatopoiimeni-odigisi-prepei-na-eggyithoyme-oti-i-aytomatopoiimeni-odigisi-einai-asfalis/ ○ https://www.reporter.gr/Oles-oi-eidhseis/542960-Events-Neo-eyrwpaiko-ergogia-th-dieykolynsh-ths-aytomaths-odhghshs ○ https://ecopress.gr/eb-neo-evropaiko-ergo-events-apo-to-episef/ ○ https://www.gocar.gr/news/feed/41508,EMP_aytonomh_odhghsh_Eyrwph.html ○ https://www.supply-chain.gr/%CE%B5%CF%85%CF%81%CF%89%CF%80%CE%B1%CF%8A%CE%BA%CF%8C-%CE%AD%CF%81%CE%B3%CE%BF-events-%CE%AD%CE%BD%CE%B1-%CE%B2%CE%AE%CE%BC%CE%B1-%CF%80%CE%B9%CE%BF-%CE%BA%CE%BF%CE%BD%CF%84%CE%AC-%CF%83%CF%84/2-391/ ○ https://neatora.gr/episey-emp-events-ena-vima-pio-konta-stin-axiopisti-aytomatopoiimeni-odigisi-se-diskoles-odikes-synt-515179.html

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://www.taxidromos.gr/topic/4350060/el/ada-sintonizei-ergo-autonomi-odigisi.html
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- *Other activity*

Table 11 EVENTS other activities between M01-M06

Date	Type of activity	URL
09/02/2023	EVENTS on CORDIS EU page	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069614

6.2 Planned activities

As far as the planned activities are concerned, EVENTS has, already, paved the way towards submitting an application for participating in the 26th IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems - ITSC 2023, EUCAD2023, and ITS Europe 2023 conferences. Moreover, it has submitted an application for being included in the CINEA brochure for CCAM, it has prepared the first paper to be submitted in the IEEE intelligent vehicles symposium and is also planning to submit an abstract at the ITS Australia Global Summit 2023.

An indicative list of suggested scientific journals and an indicative list of suggested upcoming events are, also, available in Annexes 2 and 3 respectively, for assisting partners in scheduling their upcoming communication and dissemination activities respectively. A thorough update of partners' activities will be included in the next version of the current deliverable on M18.

7. Evaluation & monitoring of activities

7.1 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Measurable targets for communication and dissemination activities have been set, since the proposal phase, in order to ensure that the desired impact is achieved. Table 12 outlines the EVENTS Key Performance Indicators for measuring communication and dissemination efforts, against their already defined baseline values.

Table 12 List of Dissemination and Communication KPIs

KPIs	Baseline Values
EVENTS brand identity (inc. logo, guidelines, templates, illustrations/graphics)	1
Factsheet & standard presentation	1&1
Brochure	2
Poster	2
Roll-up	2
Project video	1
E-newsletter	8, with a total number of 200 e-newsletter recipients
Website	1 with 100 visitors/views per month
Social Media	2 accounts with 400 members each
Media articles	15
Publications in Horizon Europe communication tools	5
Media campaigns	1
Advisory board members	6-8 (at least 3-4 of them to be outside EU)
Number of peer reviewed journal articles	5
Conference publications	10
Conference presentations	20
Organisation of workshops/special sessions	4
Number of International, EU and national projects networked	5 (at least 2 of them to be outside EU)
Number of liaison activities performed	10 (at least 4 of them to be outside EU)
Number of discussions in fora, committees, associations & organisations	12
Number of standardisation bodies and TCs networked	2
Use case demonstrations	3, with 30 people attending per event
Final Event participants	120

In the context of close, effective and efficient monitoring of the dissemination and communication activities, a KPI matrix has been developed, via using an excel spreadsheet, and it will be regularly monitored. The KPI matrix is available on the internal project's repository. It includes the KPIs' names, along with their current value and the expected achieved results by the end of the project. The following figure 27 presents the KPI matrix of M06 (February 2023) of the EVENTS project.

EVENTS Dissemination and Communication KPIs			
KPIs Names	Current values (M06)	Baseline value	Result
EVENTS brand identity (inc. logo, guidelines, templates, illustrations/graphics)	1	1	✓
Factsheet	1	1	✓
Standard presentation	1	1	✓
Brochure	1	2	✗
Poster	1	2	✗
Roll-up	1	2	✗
Project video	0	1	✗
E-newsletter	0	8	✗
e-Newsletter recipients	0	200	✗
Website	1	1	✓
Website visitors	170	100	✓
Twitter account	1	1	✓
Twitter (members)	46	400	✗
LinkedIn account	1	1	✓
LinkedIn members	61	400	✗
Media articles	9	15	✗
Publications in Horizon Europe communication tools	1	5	✗
Media campaigns	0	1	✗
Advisory board members (total number)	0	6	✗
Advisory board members (members outside EU)	0	3	✗
Number of peer reviewed journal articles	0	5	✗
Conference publications	0	10	✗
Conference presentations	1	20	✗
Organisation of workshops/special sessions	0	4	✗
Number of International, EU and national projects networked	2	5	✗
Number of International, EU and national projects networked (outside EU)	0	2	✗
Number of liaison activities performed	1	6	✗
Number of liaison activities performed (outside EU)	0	4	✗
Number of discussions in fora, committees, associations & organisations	0	12	✗
Number of standardisation bodies and TCs networked	0	2	✗
Use case demonstrations	0	3	✗
Attendees per use case demonstration	0	30	✗
Final Event participants	0	120	✗

Figure 27 EVENTS KPIs monitoring matrix

7.2 Risk management and compliance

In EVENTS, and particularly within WP7, risks are considered as an integral part of the workplan. The complexity of the problem at hand and the trans-disciplinary nature of the consortium add to the number of risky aspects that may cause issues in the project execution lifecycle. As a matter of fact, table 13 below, provides an initial attempt to identify potential risks, associated with the conduction of EVENTS dissemination, communications and social awareness activities, along with their probability of

occurrence and the corresponding impact, as well as the already defined mitigation measures per risk.

Table 13 EVENTS WP7 risk registry

Description of risk	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Low penetration of EVENTS brand name to the national, EU and international audiences [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]	EVENTS team will proceed, at the early stages of the project, with: the development of a precise communication & dissemination strategy [M06], the design of EVENTS brand story [M03] and website [M03] and the creation of dedicated social media accounts [M02]. Statistics on the use of the EVENTS webpage and social media accounts will be reviewed periodically to monitor visitors' flow and increase the diffusion in time.
Low engagement of consortium partners in dissemination/communication activities [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]	Close collaboration of WP7 Leader with all consortium partners and continuous triggering of the inactive members through bi-lateral communication and regular WP7 meetings.
Conferences and relevant exhibitions/fairs may be cancelled or postponed [Likelihood: Medium Severity: Medium]	Follow closely any relevant opportunities and strive for virtual attendance.
Exploitation plan for EVENTS results and respective innovation roadmap not viable [Likelihood: Medium Severity: High]	During the proposal phase key stakeholders have been identified and engaged to ensure a user-led business partnership. This activity will continue during the project to ensure realistic and sustainable business and exploitations plans for all.
EVENTS results are not properly promoted to standardisation bodies [Likelihood: Medium Severity: Medium]	Several partners are actively contributing in standardisation bodies. Especially WMG, which is responsible for these activities, has prominent roles in ISO, SAE and ASAM in automated driving working groups, chairing also some of them.
Confidential information is disclosed through project's dissemination/ communication activities [Likelihood: Low Severity: High]	EVENTS has identified and described the required procedures for publishing project's dissemination and communication material since the early stages of the project via its CA. All partners are obliged to follow these guidelines. It has been also established a second level of security (procedures are detailed described in Annex 1), where all information related to communication/ dissemination issues must be first approved beforehand by EVENTS Project Coordinator, EVENTS Technical Manager and the EVENTS Communication Manager/WP7 Leader.

8. Partners' roles & efforts

Successful communication, dissemination and social awareness of EVENTS rely on the commitment and contribution of all project partners. For that reason, the WP7 leader, SEAB, will be engaging with all project partners and will promote effective interaction between WP7 and all other WPs to ensure that the communication, dissemination and social awareness activities of the project are effective and impactful. All partners have been allocated person months under WP7.

Partners will contribute to the communication, dissemination and social awareness of the project through the development of the research, identifying outcomes, outputs and benefits, publishing research papers and articles, presenting the project advances in relating events, conferences, scientific fora, technical committees etc., using their extensive knowledge of contacts in relevant fields and identifying appropriate groups of stakeholders.

WP7 structure includes the following tasks (table 14) and deliverables (table 15), along with the corresponding assignments, as derived from EVENTS GA:

Table 14 EVENTS Tasks and responsible partners

Description	Leader	Contributors	Duration
Task 7.1 EVENTS Communication & dissemination	SEAB	ICCS, CRF, UULM, TECN, TUD, HIT-FR, HIT-UK, S4	M01 – M36
Task 7.2 Exploitation & innovation management	S4	CRF, SEAB, TECN, TUD, HIT-FR, APTIV, WMG	M06 – M36
Task 7.3 Standardisation & international liaison	WMG	ICCS, SEAB, TUD, HIT-FR, HIT-UK	M01 – M36
Task 7.4 Social innovation & gender equality	SEAB	HIT-FR, HIT-UK	M24 – M36

Table 15 EVENTS WP7 Deliverables

Description	Leader	Due Date	Type	Dissemination Level
D7.1 EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness	SEAB	M06	Report	Public
D7.1 EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness <i>(update)</i>	SEAB	M18	Report	Public
D7.1 EVENTS Communication, Dissemination, and social awareness <i>(update)</i>	SEAB	M36	Report	Public

D7.2 EVENTS Exploitation plan, Innovation map & Standardization activities	WMG	M12	Report	Sensitive
D7.2 EVENTS Exploitation plan, Innovation map & Standardization activities (update)	WMG	M36	Report	Sensitive

The following table 16, presents the WP7 Milestones. It is worth mentioning that the first one, namely, MS01 related to launching of the EVENTS website has been successfully and on time fulfilled.

Table 16 EVENTS Milestones

Milestone Number	Milestone Title	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date	Means of verification
MS01	EVENTS website online	SEAB	M03	Website launched
MS13	EVENTS Final event	SEAB	M36	Final event organised

It goes without saying, that a successful, impactful, effective and efficient dissemination and communication procedure, requires the continuous commitment and contribution of all project partners. Thus, adequate resources have been allocated to all partners and the total number of the Person Months (PMs) is given in table 17 below:

Table 17 EVENTS WP7 total effort in PMs

Partner's short name	ICCS	CRF/ STELLANTIS	UULM	SEAB	TECN	TUD	HIT- FR	APTIV	HIT- UK	S4	WMG
Total	98.00 PMs										

9. Conclusions

This deliverable presented the EVENTS communication, dissemination and social awareness plan and activities as part of the overall EVENTS communication, dissemination and social awareness strategy, which will be used as a guide for the consortium members towards the effective allocation of time and resources in the maximization of project's impact and outreach.

It describes EVENTS communication and dissemination strategy by defining the key concepts and objectives, the stakeholders' community that EVENTS aims to distribute its messages, along with the corresponding key messages and the channels, tools and means to be used for achieving the maximum desired outreach, the communication content as well as the overall engagement plan for the interested stakeholders.

Special focus is also given to the scientific approach and on the clustering and networking activities, that are going to be developed and implemented within the project, as well as to liaison activities with relevant initiatives, that can significantly enhance the proliferation of project's results and outcomes.

D7.1 focuses also, on the project's social awareness strategy, towards highlighting the key actions that are going to take place during the project course.

In addition, the document contains the approach for the evaluation and monitoring of communication and dissemination activities and the required information on partners' role and effort.

The EVENTS communication, dissemination and social awareness strategy and plan is considered as a flexible and adaptive living document to enrich the project's approach to communication, dissemination and social awareness and to ensure that information about the project and its outcomes are effectively communicated through its life and beyond.

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Annex 1: EVENTS Communication/ Dissemination procedures

Purpose of the procedures

The participation of any partner in a Conference, Event, Exhibition etc. as well as the performance of any/every dissemination & communication activity related to EVENTS project has to be communicated beforehand to the **EVENTS Project Coordinator** (mails of the corresponding persons are provided), **EVENTS Technical Manager** (mails of the corresponding persons are provided) and the **EVENTS Communication Manager/WP7 Leader** (mails of the corresponding persons are provided).

According to the Article 8.4 of EVENTS Consortium Agreement, '*prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication*'.

Basic objectives of the procedures

- Production of high-quality EVENTS publications, presentations and other communication material;
- Avoidance of overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Monitoring and recording of the dissemination activities of the project in an effective and efficient way;

Step by step procedure (notice for a scientific or conference publication- before initial submission)

1. Send the information notice to the EVENTS coordinator, Technical Manager & the WP7 Leader, including the paper title, the authors and the conference/journal name, before the initial submission of the publication;
2. The authors should also inform Coordinator and WP7 leader that GA & CA requirements regarding the publication are satisfied;
3. WP7 Leader will make sure that the authors are acknowledging, properly, their work as part of EVENTS funding using the right acknowledgment text;
4. The leading author will revert back to the WP7 Leader with the approval/rejection notification and the pdf paper, once it is available;

Step by step procedure (request of approval for presentations and other communication material)

1. Send the dissemination request/material to WP7 Leader for approval;
2. WP7 Leader will send the material to Coordinator & to the Technical Manager for approval;
3. Coordinator & Technical Manager will revert back to the WP7 Leader with comments -if any-;
4. WP7 Leader will make sure that the authors are acknowledging, properly, their work as part of EVENTS funding using the right acknowledgment text;
5. WP7 Leader will provide the revised material to the EVENTS related team member(s);

In case of:

A) Approval: When approval is given through the WP7 Leader, the partner(s) is (are) free to proceed with the realisation of the proposed dissemination activity;

B) Conflict/objection: Project Coordinator, Technical Manager, and Dissemination manager can reject the proposed dissemination activity if they have objections, related to overlaps or possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information concern the work performed in the different WPs. In case of conflict, the issue will be discussed among the coordinator, the WP7 Leader and the involved partners;

NOTE:

- If partners wish to re-present or release material already approved (with no modifications or changes on the content), then no formal approval is required. The WP7 Leader has to be informed. If there are no objections, then the WP7 Leader notifies the authors to proceed with the dissemination activity.

- In case a partner wishes to organise a workshop or special event related to EVENTS, then the approval of WP7 Leader and the information of the Coordinator is also needed before the realisation of this dissemination activity.

Reporting of partners' activity

Every communication activity is reported by the WP7 Leader in the online **Dissemination activities report spreadsheet**, available [here](#).

WP7 Leader is responsible for acquiring and storing the material within the WP7 Internal Repository respective folder.

Funding statement/Acknowledgement of EU funding

According to the Articles 16.3 & 17 and Annex 5 "Specific Rules" of EVENTS Grant Agreement, any communication (*including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.*) or dissemination activity *related to the action and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result* funded by the grant

must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) *(The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. and displayed at least as prominently and visibly, when displayed in association with other logos (e.g., of beneficiaries or sponsors) and funding statement* (translated into local languages, where appropriate), as of below:

For any communication activity, presentation, on-line material, hard copy/printed material, the EU emblem must be displayed, along with the phrase:

“EVENTS project is funded by the European Union, under grant agreement No 101069614. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

For any infrastructure & equipment, the EU emblem must be displayed, along with the phrase:

“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of the EVENTS project, which is funded by the European Union, under grant agreement No 101069614. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

For any (scientific) publication/technical paper, the acknowledgement must be displayed as follows:

“This research has been conducted as part of the EVENTS project, which is funded by the European Union, under grant agreement No 101069614. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

European flag (EU emblem)

Horizontal

Vertical

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

- European flag (EU emblem) can be downloaded in all EU languages and formats, via the following url: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter

The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes 2021-2027 is thoroughly described in the following url: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf

Implement open science practices

Horizon Europe Programme Guide: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf *Horizon Europe Programme Guide*

Open Research Europe, the European Commission in-house scientific publishing service

Guidelines are available here: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

Non-European Travel -Eligibility of travelling costs outside Europe

According to what it was discussed during the kick-off meeting, traveling outside Europe for attending related conferences/events can be taken for granted, if it is clearly indicated in EVENTS Grant Agreement (see section 2.2.1).

In any other case, any interested partner, must communicate (through the coordinator) his intention to participate in such an activity by notifying the PO well in advance.

In order to facilitate the whole process, the responsible partner must provide all the required relevant information about the event: a well-described conference session accompanied by a tentative agenda, as well as a convincing justification for his participation towards clearly designating the relevance of the presentation /poster etc. to EVENTS project.

Annex 2: EVENTS calendar of proposed scientific journals

Title of journal/magazine	Website	Impact Factor	OA (Open Access)/ NOA (Non-Open Access)	Description (scope and topics)
Intelligent Transportation Systems				
IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=7274857	5.009	OA	The IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles (T-IV) publishes peer-reviewed articles that provide innovative research concepts and application results, report significant theoretical findings and application case studies, and raise awareness of pressing research and application challenges in areas of intelligent vehicles in a roadway environment, and in particular in automated vehicles. The T-IV focuses on providing critical information to the intelligent vehicle community, serving as a dissemination vehicle for IEEE ITS Society members and the others to learn the state-of-the-art development and progress on research and applications in the field of intelligent vehicles.
IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems journal	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=6979	9.551	OA	The IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems is concerned with the design, analysis, and control of information technology as it is applied to transportation systems. The Transactions is focused on the numerous technical aspects of ITS technologies spanned by the IEEE. Transportation systems are invariably complex, and their complexity arises from many sources. Transportation systems can involve humans, vehicles, shipments, information technology, and the physical infrastructure, all interacting in complex ways. Many aspects of transportation systems are uncertain, dynamic and nonlinear, and such systems may be highly sensitive to perturbations. Controls can involve multiple agents that (and/or who) are distributed and hierarchical. Humans who invariably play critical roles in a transportation system have a

				diversity of objectives and a wide range of skills and education. Transportation systems are usually large-scale in nature and are invariably geographically distributed.
IET Intelligent Transport Systems Journal	https://ietresearch.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/17519578	2.568	OA	IET Intelligent Transport Systems is a Gold Open Access interdisciplinary journal devoted to research into the practical applications of intelligent transport systems and infrastructures.
Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems: Technology, Planning, and Operations	https://www.tandfonline.com/action/journalInformation?show=aimsScope&journalCode=git_s20	3.839	OA	The Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems is especially interested in research that leads to improved planning and operation of the transportation system through the application of new technologies. The journal is particularly interested in research that adds to the scientific understanding of the impacts that intelligent transportation systems can have on accessibility, congestion, pollution, safety, security, noise, and energy and resource consumption.
International Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems Research	https://www.springer.com/journal/13177	1.385	OA	This journal is the only transportation journal to report on multi-disciplinary research efforts with the goal to discover solutions to difficult issues in the field. It provides a platform to bring together researchers and specialists in the fields of transportation, electrical, mechanical and traffic engineering, as well as those in the areas of policy planning, economics, and psychology, for wide-ranging discussion about future transportation systems. The journal is the global forum for transportation research.
Journal of Advanced Transportation	https://www.hindawi.com/journals/jat/	2.249	OA	Journal of Advanced Transportation publishes theoretical and innovative papers on analysis, design, operations, optimization and planning of multi-modal transport networks, transit & traffic systems, transport technology and traffic safety.
IEEE Open Journal of Vehicular Technology	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=8782711		OA	The IEEE Open Journal of Vehicular Technology covers the theoretical, experimental and operational aspects of electrical and electronics engineering in mobile radio, motor vehicles and land transportation. (a) Mobile radio shall include all terrestrial mobile services. (b) Motor vehicles shall include the components and systems and motive power

				for propulsion and auxiliary functions. (c) Land transportation shall include the components and systems used in both automated and non-automated facets of ground transport technology.
Communication, Computing and IoT Technologies				
IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=8782661	5.900	OA	As a fully open access journal publishing high-quality peer reviewed papers, IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society covers science, technology, applications and standards for information organization, collection and transfer using electronic, optical and wireless channels and networks, including but not limited to: Systems and network architecture, control and management; Protocols, software and middleware; Quality of service, reliability and security; Modulation, detection, coding, and signaling; Switching and routing; Mobile and portable communications; Terminals and other end-user devices; Networks for content distribution and distributed computing; and Communications-based distributed resources control.
IEEE Transaction on Mobile Computing	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=7755	6.075	OA	IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing focuses on the key technical issues related to (a) architectures, (b) support services, (c) algorithm/protocol design and analysis, (d) mobile environments, (e) mobile communication systems, (f) applications, and (g) emerging technologies. Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following: a) Architectures - Mobile networks and hosts, Agents and proxies, Mobility management, mobile agent and proxy architectures Integrated wireline and wireless systems, Planning and standardization. b) Support Services - Mobility and roaming, Nomadic computing, Multimedia Operating system support, Power management. c) Algorithm/Protocol Design and Analysis - Online and mobile environments, Limited bandwidth, Intermittent connectivity. d) Mobile Environments - Data and knowledge management, Performance modeling and characterization, Security, scalability and reliability, Design, management and operation, Systems and technologies. e) Mobile

				<p>Communication Systems - Wireless, cellular and spread-spectrum systems, Multi-user and multi-access techniques and algorithms, Multi-channel processing, Channel coding, Data coding and compression. f) Applications - Location-dependent and sensitive, Nomadic computing, Wearable computers and body area networks, Multimedia applications and multimedia signal processing, Pervasive computing, Wireless sensor networks. g) Emerging Technologies.</p>
IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=7693	8.346	OA	<p>The IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications publishes high-quality manuscripts on advances in the state-of-the-art of wireless communications. Both theoretical contributions (including new techniques, concepts, and analyses) and practical contributions (including system experiments and prototypes, and new applications) are encouraged. The general scope of the Transactions includes, but is not limited to, the following: Modulation and coding, Detection and estimation, Diversity techniques and equalization, Propagation and channel characterization, Fading countermeasures, Multiuser detection, Signal separation and interference rejection, DSP applications to wireless systems, Broadband wireless communications, Network architectures and protocols, with an emphasis on physical and link layer communication, Adaptive antennas for wireless systems, Multiple access techniques, Space-time processing, Synchronization techniques, Software radio, Resource allocation and interference management, Multirate and multicarrier communications, Security, privacy, and authentication, Experimental and prototype results, Systems and services including mobile satellites, wireless local loops, wireless LANs, wireless PBX, and PCS/cellular.</p>
IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=9424	11.648	OA	<p>The IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics is a multidisciplinary journal publishing technical papers that bridge the gap between theory and application practice of informatics in industrial environments. Its scope encompasses the use of information in intelligent, distributed, agile industrial</p>

				automation and control systems. Included are knowledge-based and AI enhanced automation; intelligent computer control systems; flexible and collaborative manufacturing; industrial informatics aspects in software-defined vehicles and robotics, computer vision, industrial cyber-physical and industrial IoT systems; real-time and networked embedded systems; security in industrial processes; industrial communications; systems interoperability and human machine interaction.
Elsevier Journal of Network and Computer Applications	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-network-and-computer-applications/about/aims-and-scope	7.574	OA	The Journal of Network and Computer Applications welcomes research contributions, surveys and notes in all areas relating to computer networks and applications thereof. The following list of sample-topics is by no means to be understood as restricting contributions to the topics mentioned: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -new design techniques, interesting or novel applications, components or standards -computer networks with tools such as WWW -emerging standards for internet protocols -Wireless networks -Mobile Computing -emerging computing models such as cloud computing, grid computing -emerging network protocols such as sensor networks, delay tolerant networks, Internet of things -applications of networked systems for remote collaboration and telemedicine -applications of an educational, transactional and cooperational nature -applications of security in computer and networks
IEEE Transactions on Big Data	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=6687317	4.271	OA	The IEEE Transactions on Big Data publishes peer reviewed articles with big data as the main focus. The articles provide cross disciplinary innovative research ideas and applications results for big data including novel theory, algorithms and applications. Research areas for big data include, but are not restricted to, big data analytics, big data visualization, big data curation and management, big data semantics, big data infrastructure, big data standards, big data performance analyses, intelligence from big

				data, scientific discovery from big data security, privacy and legal issues specific to big data. Applications of big data in the fields of endeavor where massive data is generated are of particular interest.
Robotics & Automation				
International Journal of Automation and Control	https://www.inderscience.com/jhome.php?jcode=ijaac	2.060	OA	IJAAC addresses the evolution and realisation of the theory, algorithms, techniques, schemes and tools for any kind of automation and control platforms including macro, micro and nano scale machineries and systems, with emphasis on implications that state-of-the-art technology choices have on both the feasibility and practicability of the intended applications. This perspective acknowledges the complexity of the automation, instrumentation and process control methods and delineates itself as an interface between the theory and practice existing in parallel over diverse spheres.
IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=8856	6.636	OA	The IEEE Transactions on Automation Science and Engineering (T-ASE) publishes fundamental papers on Automation, emphasizing scientific results that advance efficiency, quality, productivity, and reliability. T-ASE encourages interdisciplinary approaches from computer science, control systems, electrical engineering, mathematics, mechanical engineering, operations research, and other fields. T-ASE welcomes results relevant to industries such as agriculture, biotechnology, healthcare, home automation, maintenance, manufacturing, pharmaceuticals, retail, security, service, supply chains, and transportation. T-ASE addresses a research community willing to integrate knowledge across disciplines and industries. For this purpose, each paper includes a Note to Practitioners that summarizes how its results can be applied or how they might be extended to apply in practice.
International Journal of Vehicle Autonomous Systems	https://www.inderscience.com/jhome.php?jcode=ijvas		OA	IJVAS is an established international authoritative reference in the field of vehicle autonomous systems research and development. Such systems aim to increase accident avoidance and road capacity, improve the travel experience by relieving occupants of

				driving/navigation chores, reduce total vehicle numbers and eliminate some of the services/infrastructure associated with motoring today
International Journal of Robotics Research	https://journals.sagepub.com/description/IJR	6.887	OA	A leading peer-reviewed journal in its field for more than two decades, The International Journal of Robotics Research (IJRR) was the first scholarly publication on robotics research. IJRR offers incisive and thought-provoking original research papers and articles, perceptive reviews, and lively editorials on ground-breaking trends issues, technical developments, and theories in robotics by the outstanding scholars and practitioners in the field. The Journal covers more than just narrow technical advances-it embraces a wide variety of topics.
Robotics and Automation Letters	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=7083369	4.321	OA	The IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters (RAL) publishes peer-reviewed articles that provide a timely and concise account of innovative research ideas and application results, reporting significant theoretical findings and application case studies in areas of robotics and automation.
IEEE Transactions on Robotics	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=8860	6.835	OA	The IEEE Transactions on Robotics (T-RO) publishes fundamental papers on all aspects of robotics, featuring interdisciplinary approaches from computer science, control systems, electrical engineering, mathematics, mechanical engineering, and other fields. Robots and intelligent machines and systems are critical in areas such as industrial applications; service and personal assistants; surgical operations; space, underwater, and remote exploration; entertainment; safety, search, and rescue; military applications; agriculture applications; and intelligent vehicles. Special emphasis is placed on intelligent machines and systems for unstructured environments, where a significant portion of the environment is unknown and cannot be directly sensed or controlled.
Machine Perception				

International Journal of Computer Vision	https://www.springer.com/journal/11263	13.369	OA	International Journal of Computer Vision (IJCV) details the science and engineering of this rapidly growing field. Regular articles present major technical advances of broad general interest. Survey articles offer critical reviews of the state of the art and/or tutorial presentations of pertinent topics.
IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/RecentIssue.jsp?punumber=34	24.314	OA	The IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence publishes articles on all traditional areas of computer vision and image understanding, all traditional areas of pattern analysis and recognition, and selected areas of machine intelligence, with a particular emphasis on machine learning for pattern analysis. Areas such as techniques for visual search, document and handwriting analysis, medical image analysis, video and image sequence analysis, content-based retrieval of image and video, face and gesture recognition and relevant specialized hardware and/or software architectures are also covered.

Annex 3: EVENTS indicative calendar of proposed events

Date	Event	Location	Website	Important deadlines
2022				
14-17/11/2022	TRA 2022	Lisbon, Portugal	https://traconference.eu/	
22-23/11/2022	XV SMART CITY FORUM	Warsaw, Poland	https://en.smartcityforum.pl/	
07-08/12/2022	ITS Hellas 2022	Athens, Greece	https://itshellas2021-conference.gr/	
15-16/12/2022	ICSTM 2022: 16. International Conference on Sustainable Transportation and Mobility	Cairo, Egypt	https://waset.org/sustainable-transportation-and-mobility-conference-in-december-2022-in-cairo	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: September 29, 2022 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: October 13, 2022 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: November 15, 2022
2023				
04-07/01/2023	24th International Conference On Distributed Computing And Networking	IIT Kharagpur, India	https://cse.iitkgp.ac.in/conf/ICDCN23/	
08-10/01/2023	2023 TRB Annual Meeting	Washington, D.C	https://www.trb.org/AnnualMeeting/AnnualMeeting.aspx	
30-31/01/2023	ICCV 2023: 17. International Conference on Computer Vision	Istanbul, Turkey	https://waset.org/computer-vision-conference-in-january-2023-in-istanbul	
16-20/04/2023	16th IEEE International Conference on Software Testing, Verification and Validation (ICST) 2023	Dublin, Ireland	https://conf.researchr.org/home/icst-2023#organizing-partners	
22-23/04/2023	ICMM 2024: 18. International Conference on Mobility Management	Seville, Spain	https://waset.org/mobility-management-conference-in-april-2024-in-seville	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird

				Registration Deadline: March 24, 2024
21-23/04/2023	2023 International Symposium on Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (SoCAV 2023)	Shenzhen, China	https://www.socav.org/	
26-28/04/2023	VEHITS 2023	Prague, Czech Republic	https://vehits.scitevents.org/	Regular Paper Submission: November 18, 2022 Position Paper Submission: January 19, 2023 Doctoral Consortium Paper Submission: March 1, 2023
03-04/05/2023	4th European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving (EUCAD 2023)	Brussels, Belgium	https://www.connect.edautomateddriving.eu/blog/eucad2023/	
04-05/05/2023	ICSTM 2023: 17. International Conference on Sustainable Transportation and Mobility	Singapore, Singapore	https://waset.org/sustainable-transportation-and-mobility-conference-in-may-2023-in-singapore	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: September 29, 2022 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: October 13, 2022 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: April 02, 2023
04-05/05/2023	ICAIVA 2023: 17. International Conference on Automation, Intelligent Vehicles and Applications	Istanbul, Türkiye	https://waset.org/automation-intelligent-vehicles-and-applications-conference-in-may-2023-in-istanbul	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: September 29, 2022 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: October 13, 2022 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: April 05, 2023
22-24/05/2023	15th ITS European Congress	Lisbon, Portugal	https://itseuropeancongress.com/	Call for Contribution closing deadline: 16 December 2022
28-01/06/2023	IEEE International Conference on Communications	Rome, Italy	https://icc2023.ieee-icc.org/	
18-22/06/2023	IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition 2023	Vancouver Convention Center	https://cvpr.thecvf.com/Conferences/2023/Dates	Paper Registration Deadline: 04 November 2022 Paper Submission deadline: 11 November 2022

04-07/06/2023	2023 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV 2023)	Anchorage, Alaska, USA	https://2023.ieee-iv.org/	Paper Submission Deadline: February 01, 2023
29-02/06/2023	2023 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)	London	https://www.icra2023.org/	
13-15/06/2023	ADAS & Autonomous Vehicle Technology Expo 2023	Stuttgart, Germany	https://www.autonomousvehicletechnologyexpo.com/	
15-16/06/2023	ICAIVA 2023: 17. International Conference on Automation, Intelligent Vehicles and Applications	Venice, Italy	https://waset.org/automation-intelligent-vehicles-and-applications-conference-in-june-2023-in-venice	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: September 29, 2022 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: October 13, 2022 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: February 20, 2023
18-21/06/2023	2023 IEEE 97th Vehicular Technology Conference	Florence, Italy	https://events.vtsociety.org/vtc2023-spring/	Paper submission deadline: 12 December 2022
22-23/06/2023	ICCTM 2023: 17. International Conference on Connected Transportation and Mobility	Online	https://waset.org/connected-transportation-and-mobility-conference-in-june-2023-in-paris	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: September 29, 2022 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: October 13, 2022 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: May 25, 2023
14-15/07/2023	Automotive and Autonomous Systems 2023	Berlin, Germany	https://www.lexismeting.com/automotive	
24-25/07/2023	ICAV 2023: 17. International Conference on Autonomous Vehicles	Zurich, Switzerland	https://waset.org/autonomous-vehicles-conference-in-july-2023-in-zurich	
16-17/09/2023	ICIF 2023: 17. International Conference on Information Fusion	Rome, Italy	https://waset.org/information-fusion-conference-in-september-2023-in-rome	
17-20/09/2023	18th Conference on Computer Science and Intelligence	Warsaw, Poland	https://fedcsis.org/2023/node	Technical sessions proposal submission: November 14, 2022 Paper submission (sharp / no

	Systems FedCSIS 2023			extension): May 23, 2023 Position paper submission: June 7, 2023
19-22/09/2023	42nd International Conference on Computer Safety, Reliability and Security (SafeComp 2023)	Toulouse, France	https://safecomp2023.cnrs.fr/	Workshop proposal submission: February 5, 2023 Abstract submission: February 6, 2023 Full paper submission: February 13, 2023
24-28/09/2023	26th IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC 2023)	Bilbao, Spain	https://2023.ieee-itsc.org/	February 15, 2023 — Proposal due for special sessions March 1, 2023 – Proposal due for workshops/tutorials/industrial sessions May 15, 2023 – Submission deadline for regular, special session, and workshop papers June 30, 2023 – Notification of paper acceptance July 31, 2023 – Final paper submission deadline
13-14/12/2023	ICSTM 2023: 17. International Conference on Sustainable Transportation and Mobility	Cairo, Egypt	https://waset.org/sustainable-transportation-and-mobility-conference-in-december-2023-in-cairo	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: September 29, 2022 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: October 13, 2022 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: November 15, 2023
TBU	IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. on Intell. Robots and Syst. (IROS)			
TBU	Autonomous Vehicles Summit 2023			
2024				
18-19/01/2024	ICCCAM 2024: 18. International Conference on Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility	Rome, Italy	https://waset.org/cooperative-connected-and-automated-mobility-conference-in-january-2024-in-rome	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: December 17, 2023
16-20/09/2024	30th ITS World Congress	Dubai, United Arab Emirates	https://itsworldcongress.com/	

21-22/10/2024	ICCTM 2024: 18. International Conference on Connected Transportation and Mobility	London, United Kingdom	https://waset.org/connected-transportation-and-mobility-conference-in-october-2024-in-london	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: June 23, 2024
18-19/11/2024	ICCAVM 2024: 18. International Conference on Connected and Automated Vehicle Mobility	London, United Kingdom	https://waset.org/connected-and-automated-vehicle-mobility-conference-in-november-2024-in-london	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: July 27, 2024
3-4/05/2024	ICSTM 2024: 18. International Conference on Sustainable Transportation and Mobility	Singapore, Singapore	https://waset.org/sustainable-transportation-and-mobility-conference-in-may-2024-in-singapore	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: April 02, 2024
6-7/05/2024	ICAIVA 2024: 18. International Conference on Automation, Intelligent Vehicles and Applications	Istanbul, Turkey	https://waset.org/automation-intelligent-vehicles-and-applications-conference-in-may-2024-in-istanbul	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: April 05, 2024
17-18/06/2022	ICEEVT 2024: 18. International Conference on E-mobility and Emerging Vehicular Technology	Chisinau, Moldova	https://waset.org/e-mobility-and-emerging-vehicular-technology-conference-in-june-2024-in-chisinau	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: May 17, 2024
21-22/06/2024	ICEEVT 2024: 18. International Conference on E-mobility and Emerging Vehicular Technology	Vienna, Austria	https://waset.org/e-mobility-and-emerging-vehicular-technology-conference-in-june-2024-in-vienna	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready)

				Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: May 20, 2024
21-22/06/2024	ICAIVA 2024: 18. International Conference on Automation, Intelligent Vehicles and Applications	Venice, Italy	https://waset.org/automation-intelligent-vehicles-and-applications-conference-in-june-2024-in-venice	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: February 20, 2024
24-25/06/2024	ICCTM 2024: 18. International Conference on Connected Transportation and Mobility	Paris, France	https://waset.org/connected-transportation-and-mobility-conference-in-june-2024-in-paris	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: May 25, 2024
19-20/08/2024	ICCCAM 2024: 18. International Conference on Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility	London, United Kingdom	https://waset.org/cooperative-connected-and-automated-mobility-conference-in-august-2024-in-london	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline : April 20, 2024
13-14/12/2024	ICSTM 2024: 18. International Conference on Sustainable Transportation and Mobility	Cairo, Egypt	https://waset.org/sustainable-transportation-and-mobility-conference-in-december-2024-in-cairo	Abstracts/Full-Text Paper Submission Deadline: July 31, 2023 Notification of Acceptance/Rejection: August 30, 2023 Final Paper (Camera Ready) Submission & Early Bird Registration Deadline: November 15, 2024